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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the “*Low-damage Multi-pass Electron Microscopy*” *Interdisciplinary Training Webinar* - the second in the planned series of 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars for the Q-SORT project.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars are part of Work Package 3 **Theory, optical testing, and TEM implementation of generalised Sorter** [Months: 1-41], Task 3.5 - Interdisciplinary Training Webinars (M6, M11, M12, M18, M24, M26, M30, M36, M41).

The present document is comprised of 4 Chapters, including Introduction and Conclusions.

The Introduction describes what a webinar is.

Chapter 2 summarises what we mean by Interdisciplinary Training Webinars and what their function is within Q-SORT.

Chapter 3 illustrates context, aims, and content of the second Interdisciplinary Training Webinar of Q-SORT.

The conclusions outline future plans for the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHAT IS A WEBINAR?

A webinar is a web-based seminar which can be streamed either live or on demand. It might be just a simple audio stream, or it might include visual aids, such as PowerPoint slides, recorded video clips, or live software demonstrations.

The experience of a webinar attempts to reproduce the benefits of attending a seminar. Audience members can ask questions and the speaker can survey or poll the audience and get feedback as he or she delivers the information.

Webinar technology providers need to support these interactive elements in addition to the basic delivery of the audio and video streams. Keyboard chat features and Q&A are usually subject to more control, whereby the presenters can see messages from the audience and choose whether to broadcast them to all participants, ignore them, or reply privately.

The Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Webinars make use of Vimeo as a platform for playback and of Facebook Live as a platform for live streaming. We chose these platforms as they provide the best value for money and offer the added advantage of being very widespread. On both platforms, users are able to pose questions by posting comments below the video. Answers can be provided by specialists during or after the webinar.

2 THE Q-SORT INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINARS

The Q-SORT project is intrinsically interdisciplinary, being born from the cross-fertilisation of three subjects: light optics (UG, MPI), electron microscopy (CNR, FZJ, UMR, FEI), and biology (MU).

The silo-breaking nature of Q-SORT provides added value through the following cross-fertilisation dynamics: microscopists borrow techniques from light optics specialists and explain back the challenges of the new measurements; biologists explain to physicists the problems that usually arise when studying proteins and suggest alternative proteins for investigation; physicists develop the quantum mechanical approach for cryo-TEM; biologists communicate a priori knowledge to light optics theoreticians in order to streamline efforts in the project work-packages (WP3-WP5).

In order to facilitate mutual learning between physicists and biologists, as well as to foster possible further applications to biology and the life sciences, 9 Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinars have been planned during the lifetime of the project. Their main aim is to function as aids to facilitate the highly interdisciplinary work in WP3 and in the other research WPs. They will do so by providing opportunities for training and mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, for forging a common language, for exchanging ideas for further joint research.

However important their role within Q-SORT, these seminars are meant for everyone, hence the choice to propose them as webinars, so as to reach as wide an audience as possible.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars introduce a sort of 'intermediate level' in the communication of science: i.e. their nature is intermediate between the specialist-to-specialist character of discipline-specific colloquia, talks, and articles and the broad appeal of conventional public understanding of science.

This is why, besides their facilitating function within WP3 and the other research WPs, the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process. Together with the Website, they ensure that Q-SORT will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

In the following paragraph we describe the second of the 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars planned for Q-SORT.

3 THE Q-SORT SECOND INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR:

LOW-DAMAGE MULTI-PASS ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

The “*Low-damage Multi-pass Electron Microscopy*” *Interdisciplinary Training Webinar* was recorded and webcast on 28 May 2018, during the first [International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time](#) at [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#). The conference was organised by Q-SORT and the “[Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms](#)” DIP project (*Deutsch-Israelische Projekt cooperation grant*) with the support of [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#) and the [Nanoscience Institute of CNR \(CNR-NANO\)](#).

The webinar featured one of conference invited speakers, **Prof. Mark Kasevich (Stanford University, USA)**.

Webinar views peaked at 8990 for the conference of Mark Kasevich (Stanford University, USA). Facebook posts related to the webinars reached over 60k people.

The webinar was recorded with one camera, then stored on remote servers for successive on-demand viewing.

The content of the Webinar was agreed upon by the Project Coordinator, Dr. Vincenzo Grillo (CNR) with Prof. Mark Kasevich (Stanford University, USA) and Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED).

The webinar can be re-watched on demand: interested parties can re-play it at their convenience by clicking on the following link:

<https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/videos/1281496401983728/>

3.1 DESCRIPTION

The webinar touches upon the following topics:

- multi-pass TEM
- live-cell electron microscopy
- phase-contrast electron microscopy
- quantum coherence
- entanglement of electrons
- dark-field microscopy
- ptychography.

The webinar illustrates various approaches being pursued in order achieve to multi-pass electron microscopy and summarises the recent efforts in this field by the group of Prof. Kasevich at Stanford, which at present is the only one in the world to have built such a machine. The webinar was aimed at:

- spreading awareness amongst physicists of the new possibilities afforded by multi-pass techniques
- exchanging ideas between scientists for furthering joint research
- promoting dialogue between the physics and biology/biochemistry communities, establishing a common language between the two disciplines.

A lively Q&A session followed after the webinar.

Simulated multi-pass TEM image of
MARV VP35. 12 passes, $4e/A^2$ dose.
Scale bar is 2 nm.

Figure 1 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 2

Figure 2 - Screenshot from Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar no. 2

4 CONCLUSIONS

This is the second Interdisciplinary Training Webinar produced for Q-SORT by [QED](#), with additional support from partner [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#).

In the past few years we have seen a consistent rise in the popularity and value of webinars as an essential training, communication, and engagement tool.

The video of the webinar also offers a unique opportunity for engagement. The project will continue to promote on-demand webinars so that their audiences will get larger and more engaged, and spend more time watching webinars, both live and on-demand. In planning the next webinars we will evaluate the effectiveness of this previous ones and use it as a guideline to help the Q-SORT consortium create, promote, and deliver even more successful webinars.

ANNEX 1: LOW DAMAGE MULTI PASS ELECTRON MICROSCOPY - SLIDES

Low damage electron microscopy

Can living samples be non-destructively imaged with electrons?

Live Cell Electron Microscopy Is Probably Impossible

Niels de Jonge^{1,2} and Diana B. Peckys³

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³Department of Biophysics, Stanford University, D-66421 Hamburg/Saar, Germany

Exploit quantum coherence to develop new low-damage/damage-free microscopy protocols

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Prior work:

Yurke, PRL 56, 15 (1986)

Putnam and Yanik, PRA 80, 040902R (2009)

Okamoto, PRA 85, 043810 (2012)

Multi-pass electron microscopy

Transcription
regulator Prfa and
30-bp DNA.
PNAS, 2016

Dose: 4 e/A²
60 keV, m = 12 passes
Single protein
(multi-slice simulation)

Proteins as TEM image targets

Bovine Mitochondrial Peroxiredoxin III

Energy	Phase shift	Incl. loss (20 nm ice)
10 keV	0.26 rad	0.39
60 keV	0.13 rad	0.125
300 keV	0.06 rad	0.055

Phase contrast imaging noise

For uncorrelated particles:

“Shot-noise” – physical origin is randomness of wavefunction collapse in quantum mechanics

How Cryo-EM Became so Hot

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2017.11.016>

Dose limited resolution limited by shot noise

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Quantum correlated (entangled) atomic ensembles

Consider $N \sim 1e6$ atoms, each in a quantum superposition of two ground state energy levels.

Measure probability of finding atoms in one of these states:

Entangled atoms

Reduced read-out noise

This data: 20 dB variance reduction

Uncorrelated atoms

"Shot-noise" Coin-toss statistics

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O. Hosten, et al., Nature (2016).

Entanglement

Atom-cavity interactions are used to create entangled many-atom quantum states.

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Low noise/damage electron microscopy

? Are there related methods
that can be employed for
electron microscopy

Prior work:
Yurke, PRL 56, 15 (1986)
Okamoto, Phys. Rev. A 85, 043810 (2012)

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Multi-pass phase measurement

Approach:
Make the phase shift large
with multiple passes
through the sample.

*Signal is larger
(larger phase shift)*

Detection noise unchanged

Signal-to-noise improves

Higgins et al., Nature 450, 15, (2007).
Tolansky (Academic Press, 1970).

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... as an optimal phase measurement strategy

PRL **96**, 010401 (2006)

PHYSICAL REVIEW LETTERS

week ending
13 JANUARY 2006

Quantum Metrology

Vittorio Giovannetti,¹ Seth Lloyd,² and Lorenzo Maccone³

Conclusions.—State preparation is the primary factor in boosting the precision of the parameter estimation, while entangled measurements are never necessary. A \sqrt{N} precision enhancement over what can be attained with a classical parallel strategy is typically obtained by using an input state that is entangled on a basis of eigenstates of H (the generator of the unitary U_φ) and by measuring a set of projectors on a basis dual to that. Schematic: (1) entangle N probes on the basis of eigenstates of H ; (2) let the probes interact with the system; (3) measure on a dual basis. Result: a \sqrt{N} precision enhancement. This is clearly related to the fact that entangled states can evolve faster than unentangled configurations employing the same resources [18]. Alternatively, a multiround protocol can achieve the same optimal precision at the expense of a larger running time.

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Optical multi-pass detection of 80 nm nanosphere

Nanosphere is undetectable at $m=1$, and $\sim 100\times$ brighter at $m=11$.

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Juffmann, et al., Nat. Comm. 2016

Multipass optical absorption imaging

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Dark field multipass of red blood cells

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Multi-pass electron microscopy

Animation credit:
Colin Ophus,
NCEM, LBNL

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Prototype resonator

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10 keV multipass TEM prototype

In partnership with
DeLong and
Electronoptica
(M. Mankos)

Moore Foundation
funded

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Column layout

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Column design

10 kV beam energy
4 nm resolution

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Laser triggered electron source

Fast electron pulses (100 psec and shorter) produced by photo-excitation from tip

Hommelhoff, PRL, 2006

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Gated mirror RF analysis

ANSYS
HFSS
simulation for
gated mirror

(S. Koppell)

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Prototype gated mirror

Prototype used to evaluate transient electrode response

Transient analysis/improperly short gate pulse

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Resonator

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Resonator

Cavity simulation (red, field rays; blue, image rays).

Column resonator and outcoupling

Figure 4: Rays start at the sample plane, bounce off of the mirror on the left, and are then out-coupled on the right.

Resonator and objective lens designs

Objective

2 nm blur

Resonator

2 nm blur

Illumination and projection

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Imaging simulations

C. Ophus,
NCEM

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Simulation/image formation

C. Ophus,
NCEM

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Multi-pass TEM Simulations

For multi-pass TEM, $m \sim 10 - 20$ is realistic.
 Phase shift ~ 0.1 rad/pass.

Single exposure images of DNA below known damage threshold

Ptychography for 5MZO

5MZO

5MZO is a protein structure from the Chlamydomonas reinhardtii genome.

See <https://www.rcsb.org/structure/5MZO> for more information.

C. Ophus,
NCEM

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~2-4 Å resolution, 20 e/Å²

3D reconstructions

C. Ophus,
NCEM

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Test image simulations/dark field

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Test image simulations of a liquid cell

20 nm diameter x 10 nm thick liquid cell.

Contrast is generated with an ideal dark field aperture.

Coherence

R.A. Herring / *Ultramicroscopy* 104 (2005) 261–270

Zero energy loss, 5 eV window

-18 eV plasmon peak, 5 eV window

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Image formation/Inelastic scattering

H. Lichte, B. Freitag / Ultramicroscopy 81 (2000) 177–186

LaB₆, zero loss
(5eV window)

LaB₆, -25 eV loss
(5eV window)

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Efficient Interaction Free Measurement

Damage probability $\sim 1/m$

(m passes through the interferometer)

Not well suited to TEM since targets are weakly absorbing and dispersive

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Concept and demonstration with photons:
Kwiat, Weinfurter, Herzog, Zielinger, Kasevich,
PRL (1995)

Proposal for electrons:
Putnam and Yanik (2009)

Multi-pass and Interaction Free Measurement

Consider a dispersive, weakly absorbing object:

Phase shift: ϕ Absorption: α

Dark field signal: $\sim m^2 \phi^2$ ($\phi \gg \alpha$)

Detection criterion: $nm^2 \phi^2 = 1$ n is the number of
probe electrons

Damage: $nm\alpha = \alpha/m\phi^2 \sim 1/m$

← for TEM proteins

(same limit obtained for phase contrast microscopy)

Multi-pass shows same damage scaling as previous IFM.
Scaling verified with full simulation.

For multi-pass TEM, $m \sim 10 - 20$ is realistic.

Counter-factual measurements

Fig. 1. Mach-Zehnder type particle interferometer. Detector D_2 clicks only if one of the arms of the interferometer is blocked by an object.

Elitzur and Vaidman, Found. Phys. (1993)

Interferometer aligned for D_2 as dark if no object in arm.

If detection at D_2 , object must be in arm, but photon not absorbed.

Detection is damage/interaction-free (certified by quantum mechanics).

Applies to multi-pass protocol (to certify, require detection of inelastically and elastically scattered electrons, or deterministic source).

Other efficient IFM protocols

For weakly absorptive and dispersive targets:

Thomas, Kohstall, Kruit, Hommelhoff, PRA (2014)

Can show damage $\alpha/m\phi^2 \sim 1/m$
(same as for multi-pass)

Supports operating modes with $m\phi \gg 1$

Likely limited by beamsplitter absorption

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Peter Kruit (Delft)
Karl Berggren (MIT)

Colin Ophus (NCEM)
Bob Glaeser (Berkeley)

Marian Mankos (ElectronOptica)
Delong Instruments

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ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL